

SS2022 SE 231.124
Nanomaterial Applications

The Titanium Dioxide Case

What is TiO_2

Titanium dioxide is the naturally occurring oxide of titanium with a wide range of applications, from paint, sunscreen to food coloring and drug matrix and coating.

Production volumes

Global titanium dioxide market share, by application, 2018

GLOBAL TITANIUM DIOXIDE MARKET: KEY DRIVERS AND FIGURES

KEY MARKET FIGURES

PAINTS AND COATINGS

In 2016, paints and coatings dominated the global market with a share of 58%.

UVA/B FILTERS IN SUNSCREENS

It has been found that people who use sunscreen daily have 24% less skin aging.

THE MARKET IN APAC

By volume, the titanium dioxide market in APAC was 2,829.9 thousand metric tons in 2016.

GLOBAL MARKET GROWTH

**1,331.3
METRIC TONS**
INCREMENTAL GROWTH

No harmonized CLP Classification for TiO₂

Hazard classification	Hazard statement	Nr. of submitters
Not classified		2387
Acute Tox 4 – H332	Harmful if inhaled	63
Acute Tox 4 H312	Harmful in contact with skin	4
Acute Tox 4 H302	Harmful if swallowed	14
Skin Irrit 2 – H315	Causes skin irritation	11
Eye Irrit 2 – H319	Causes serious eye irritation	71
STOT SE 2 – H371	May cause damage to organs	10
Resp Sens 1 – H334	May cause allergy or asthma symptoms or breathing difficulties if inhaled	1
STOT SE 3 – H335	May cause respiratory irritation	76
STOT SE 1 – H372	Cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure	69
STOT SE 2 – H373	May cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure	1
Muta 2 – H341	Suspected of causing genetic effects	1
Carc 1B – H350	May cause cancer	9
Carc 2 – H351	Suspected of causing cancer	115
Aqua Chronic 4 – H413	May cause long lasting harmful effects to aquatic life	22

Regulation of substances on the market

European chemicals agency (ECHA) and the Member States developed risk-based criteria for the selection of substances for the Community rolling action plan CoRAP. Member States and ECHA will only include substances in the CoRAP **where a request for further information may help to clarify the initial concern for that substance.**

Justification for the selection of a candidate CoRAP substance Substance Name (Public Name):

Titanium dioxide

Chemical Group:

EC Number: 236-675-5

CAS Number: 13463-67-7

Submitted by: FRANCE

Published: 20/03/2013

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (Suspected) CMR	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Wide dispersive use	<input type="checkbox"/> Cumulative exposure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (Suspected) Sensitiser	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consumer use	<input type="checkbox"/> High RCR
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (Suspected) PBT/vPvB	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exposure of sensitive populations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Aggregated tonnage
<input type="checkbox"/> Suspected endocrine disruptor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (provide further details below)	

Result of the regulation process

Titanium dioxide: E171 no longer considered safe when used as a food additive

Published: 6 May 2021

Contents

- FAQ – EFSA 2021 safety assessment of titanium dioxide (E171)
- How to contact us
- Related topic(s)

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/titanium-dioxide-e171-no-longer-considered-safe-when-used-food-additive>

EFSA has updated its safety assessment of the food additive titanium dioxide (E 171), following a request by the European Commission in March 2020.

TiO₂ classification and food ban

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The Titanium Dioxide Case Topics

**Group 1: French Carcinogenic Classification/Labeling Request, 2016,
Inhalation Route, ANSES CLH Report**

**Group 2: EU E171/TiO₂ in Food Ban, 2022, Oral Route, European Commission
Regulation**

Group 1: Carcinogenic Classification/Labeling Request, 2016, Inhalation Route, French ANSES

2016, French ANSES proposed an EU harmonized classification and labeling of TiO₂ as carcinogen 1B, H350i (all forms). Proposed code H350i “May cause cancer by inhalation route”.

Your Tasks:

1) Present a synopsis, introduce the TiO₂ context, summarize the studies giving rise for above concerns (based on the ANSES CLH report, p. 1-69); focus on the four non-human studies for the inhalation route (p. 17-18) and the human cohort studies (p. 39-41). Present your perspective. Address critical questions, such as the quality of the evidence (e.g. exposure model), possible limitations and the transferability to humans.

2) Paper presentation:

Danielsen et al.; **Effects of physicochemical properties of TiO₂ nanomaterials for pulmonary inflammation, acute phase response and alveolar proteinosis in intratracheally exposed mice.** Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology. 2020 Jan 1;386:114830. doi: 10.1016/j.taap.2019.114830.

Group 2: TiO₂'s (Food additive E171)

Genotoxicity can not be ruled out, EFSA

2021, European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) concluded, that E171's genotoxicity can not be ruled out based on available evidence and alongside with high uncertainty. Thus, E171 can not be longer considered as safe and the European Commission implemented an E171 food ban starting in 2022.

Your Tasks:

1) Present a synopsis, introduce the E171/TiO₂ context, summarize the findings giving rise for above concerns and uncertainties (based on EFSA's scientific opinion p. 1-21,); summarize the key finding of general and organ toxicity (p.22-25). Present your perspective. Address critical questions, such as the quality of the evidence (e.g. exposure model), possible limitations and the transferability to humans.

2) Paper presentation:

Bettini, S. *et al.* **Food-grade TiO₂ impairs intestinal and systemic immune homeostasis, initiates preneoplastic lesions and promotes aberrant crypt development in the rat colon.** *Sci Rep* 7, 40373 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep40373>

Thank you!